

Long-term reduced tillage does not enhance crop yield, soil organic carbon stocks or greenhouse gas mitigation under ambient rainfall and rainfall exclusion in a temperate Luvisol

Antonios Apostolakis^{a,b,1,*}, Oliver Lindunda Daka^{a,2}

^a Department of Crop Sciences, Division Agronomy, University of Goettingen, Goettingen 37073, Germany

^b Environment Modeling, Institute of Crop Science and Resource Conservation, University of Bonn, Bonn 53113, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Reduced tillage (RT) is widely promoted as an agroecological practice to enhance soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration and mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. However, its long-term effects on SOC stocks, crop yields, and soil GHG fluxes remain debated, particularly under changing climatic conditions. We investigated the impacts of RT and conventional tillage (CT) in the Garte-Sued field trial established in 1970 in Goettingen, Germany on a silt loam Haplic Luvisol under a humid temperate climate. Over two years, we assessed crop yield, SOC stocks and fractions, soil mineral N, and soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes under ambient rainfall and 50 % rainfall exclusion (via rainout shelters). After 53 years, RT resulted in a stratification of SOC within the plough layer, but SOC stocks at 0–90 cm did not differ between tillage practices. Crop yields were, in general, lower under RT compared to CT but the significance of the effect depended on crop species. Rainfall exclusion did not significantly affect yields or cumulative CO₂ and N₂O fluxes, likely due to high soil water retention and moderate water deficit. Soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes were mainly driven by soil temperature, water-filled pore space, and mineral N, with emission peaks following management events. Reduced tillage did not affect soil CO₂ efflux, while it tended to increase N₂O fluxes, especially under reduced rainfall. Our findings suggest that, in humid temperate and medium-textured soils, RT does not enhance crop yield, SOC stocks, or GHG mitigation relative to CT under ambient and reduced rainfall.

1. Introduction

Reducing tillage intensity with conservation tillage practices like no-till or reduced tillage (RT) is often considered as an agroecological practice that promotes carbon (C) sequestration in the topsoil. Since it does not rely on exogenous organic matter (OM), such as animal manure, biochar or plant residues grown elsewhere, the accrued soil organic carbon (SOC) by reducing tillage intensity has an actual carbon dioxide (CO₂) mitigation potential (Powlson et al., 2011) offering a

prospect for climate change mitigation. However, there are concerns that this may come at the expense of increased nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, potentially offsetting climate mitigation benefits (Haas et al., 2022; Li et al., 2005; Lugato et al., 2018). Therefore, the impacts of reduced tillage intensity compared to conventional tillage (CT) on SOC stocks, crop yields, and soil greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes remain debated (Bavin et al., 2009), particularly in the long-term. As climate change alters C and nitrogen (N) cycling, the effectiveness of RT for sustainable agriculture must be evaluated under current and

* Correspondence to: Department of Crop Sciences, Division Agronomy, Von-Siebold-Strasse 8, Goettingen 37075, Germany.

E-mail addresses: antonios.apostolakis@uni-goettingen.de (A. Apostolakis), oliverldaka@gmail.com (O.L. Daka), paulina.englert@uni-goettingen.de (P. Englert), stefan.siebert@uni-goettingen.de (S. Siebert), ameijide@uni-bonn.de (A. Meijide).

¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6418-189X>

² <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7027-1373>

³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6701-2020>

⁴ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9998-0672>

⁵ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6680-2186>

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experimentally induced extreme climate conditions.

Crop yield responses to practices that reduce tillage intensity are variable, and neutral and negative effects have been reported in temperate and cool climates, as well as in regions where water does not limit primary production (Angers et al., 1997; Arango and Rice, 2021; Dimassi et al., 2014; Klopp et al., 2024; van Balen et al., 2023; van Kessel et al., 2013). Negative effects are generally linked to weed infestations and residue accumulation, which hinder seedbed preparation, as well as soil compaction, while positive effects may arise from improved soil structure and biological activity (Abid and Lal, 2009; Newton et al., 2012; Soane et al., 2012; van Balen et al., 2023). As crop type and local pedoclimatic conditions play a significant role in crop yield responses to tillage practice, crop yield should always be considered when evaluating the potential of a tillage practice to promote agricultural sustainability.

While RT is promoted for its potential to increase SOC in the topsoil, evidence suggests that RT does not necessarily increase SOC stocks compared to CT when the ploughing layer and the subsoil are also considered under temperate climates, or in regions where water does not limit primary production (Angers et al., 1997; Chenu et al., 2019; Haddaway et al., 2017; Minasny et al., 2017; Skadell et al., 2023). It is less clear how RT might influence OM pools with distinct traits, such as the particulate organic matter (POM) and the mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) (Panagea et al., 2022; Prairie et al., 2023), especially in the long-term. RT practices incorporate plant residues to a shallower depth than CT practices (Dimassi et al., 2014; Staley et al., 1988), which might result in greater POM in that layer and, potentially, greater MAOM formation. As soil texture and climatic conditions strongly influence the capacity of a soil to sequester C (Georgiou et al., 2022; Poepplau et al., 2020), they might also determine its response to tillage practice. Therefore, studies should investigate the long-term effects of RT on SOC and OM pools in the topsoil and the subsoil and interpret their results in the context of their pedoclimatic conditions.

Tillage practices and events have a strong effect on soil structure and OM dynamics, on soil aeration and water retention as well as on microbial communities (Abid and Lal, 2009; Ahl et al., 1998; Apostolakis et al., 2017; Jacobs et al., 2011; Pagliai et al., 2004; Panagea et al., 2022; Pires et al., 2017) and, therefore, they can indirectly influence soil GHG fluxes, particularly those of CO₂ and N₂O. Based on recent meta-analyses, RT could result in marginal increases in N₂O emissions compared to CT (Grados et al., 2022), while others found no significant differences between RT and CT globally (Yao et al., 2024) or when focusing on cool and temperate climates (Mei et al., 2018; van Kessel et al., 2013). However, several field studies have reported increased soil N₂O fluxes under practices that reduce tillage intensity compared to CT (Pelster et al., 2021; Venterea et al., 2005). This variability in N₂O flux responses to tillage practice is presumably linked to differences in site-specific pedoclimatic conditions, crop properties, and regional management practices as well as the time elapsed since RT adoption between studies (Mei et al., 2018; van Kessel et al., 2013; Yao et al., 2024). Regarding the latter, there is a notable lack of studies investigating soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes after long-term implementations of RT in field trials.

As climate change alters C and N cycling, we need to evaluate the effects of agroecological practices, such as reducing tillage intensity, not only under current climatic conditions but also under experimentally induced extreme conditions. Such studies would help improve our understanding of the adaptation and mitigation potential of agroecology to a changing climate. However, studies investigating this are scarce and, to our knowledge, there are no studies on the interacting effects of reduced rainfall (i.e., via rainfall exclusion) and RT on soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes.

In this study, the long-term impacts of RT (applied as rotary harrowing to 7–10 cm) vs. CT (applied as mouldboard ploughing to 27–30 cm) were investigated during two years with respect to crop yield, SOC stocks and fractions, and soil GHG fluxes under both ambient rainfall and reduced rainfall by 50 % (via experimental interception).

Our objectives were to i) quantify the long-term impacts of RT and CT on SOC stocks, OM pools and crop yield, ii) evaluate how these tillage practices influence soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes, and iii) determine the response of soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes under CT and RT to reduced rainfall. We hypothesized that long-term RT has i) similar crop yields as CT under ambient rainfall and higher than CT under reduced rainfall, ii) higher SOC stocks than CT in the harrowing layer but similar SOC stocks as CT when the ploughing layer and the subsoil are considered, and iii) higher soil N₂O emissions than CT both under ambient and reduced rainfall conditions.

2. Methods

2.1. Study site

The Garte-Sued field trial (51° 48' N, 9° 93' E) is located at the Reinschhof Experimental Farm of the University of Goettingen, approximately 7 km south of Goettingen, Germany at an altitude of 165 m above sea level. According to Koeppen-Geiger classification, the region has a humid temperate climate (Cfb). The mean annual temperature and precipitation (\pm stand. deviation) were $9.6 \pm 0.7^\circ\text{C}$ and 628 ± 112 mm in the period 1982–2022 (Fig. S1) based on data from the Weather Station Goettingen (51° 50' N, 9° 95' E) of the German meteorological service. The soil of the trial is characterized as a silt loam Haplic Luvisol according to IUSS Working Group WRB (2015), with a composition of 73 % silt and 15 % clay at 0–30 cm (Jacobs et al., 2009), and therefore considered a medium-textured soil (following the definition in Weil and Brady, 2017).

The Garte-Sued field trial was established in 1970 for the comparison of CT and RT, applied annually with mouldboard ploughing to a depth of 27–30 cm and rotary harrowing to a depth of 7–10 cm, respectively (Photo S1). Before the initiation of the trial, the entire field was an arable cropland under CT (Jacobs et al., 2009). The trial follows a randomized block design with four blocks each having four plots (Fig. S2). Each plot is 20 m \times 40 m with the exception of the four western plots that are 18 m \times 40 m. Except for the tillage practice, agricultural management is applied uniformly on the entire trial. All crop residues return to the field and are incorporated into soil with soil harrowing at 5 cm shortly after harvest.

The field trial follows regional management practices and crop rotations. Details on soil and crop management are given on Table S1 and available information on crop rotations since 1970 are given in Table S2. Our study took place from 2022–10–02 to 2025–03–10. Winter wheat was sown on 2022–10–13 and harvested on 2023–08–16. Subsequently, winter barley was sown on 2023–09–25 and harvested on 2024–07–08. On 2024–08–26, a mixture of cover crops was sown on the field and incorporated on 2025–03–10. All plots received the same amount and type of fertilization.

On 2023–02–20, we installed rainout shelters in eight plots of the trial (Fig. S2), leading to a two-factor design. Rainout shelters were designed to exclude 50 % of every rainfall event using V-shaped, clear and UV transparent acrylic glass bands, following the design proposed by Kundel et al. (2018). Rainout shelters had an area of 2.5 m \times 2.5 m, and a 1 m \times 1 m square at the center of the shelter was considered as effective rainfall exclusion area, where measurements were taken. Rainout shelters remained continuously on the field until 2025–03–10 and were only temporally removed to facilitate management activities (Table S1). A barrier extending from 20 cm soil depth to 5 cm above surface was installed around each rainout shelter to prevent surface runoff from entering the sheltered area.

2.2. Aboveground biomass and crop yield

Aboveground crop biomass was determined at the time of harvest for winter wheat (2022–23) and for winter barley (2023–24) and two months prior to incorporation for the cover crop (2024–25). Crop

biomass was determined both in the open field under 100 % rainfall in all 16 plots and under the eight rainout shelters with 50 % rainfall. Under 100 % rainfall, crop biomass was determined in randomly selected 1 m × 1 m areas. Under 50 % rainfall, crop biomass was determined in 1 m × 0.2 m rectangle areas adjacent to N₂O-rings which were as undisturbed as possible. Aboveground biomass was clipped at 2 cm aboveground and separated to stubble and grain biomass. Biomass was dried at 60°C for 48 h after which it was weighed, and half the sample was dried further at 105°C for 48 h to determine water content while the rest was ground and an aliquot was used for C and N content analysis with a “vario EL cube” (Elementar, Langensfeld, Germany). For the cover crop (2024–25), aboveground biomass was sampled only in randomly selected 1 m × 1 m areas (outside GHG rings) under 100 % rainfall.

2.3. Soil bulk density

Soil bulk density was determined at 10 cm depth intervals at 0–60 cm soil depth. One pit for each tillage practice was opened on 2023–05–03 at the buffer zones between plots (Fig. S2). Pits were 70 cm deep and covered an area 50 cm × 50 cm. In each 10 cm depth interval, six pre-weighed and labelled Kopecky rings with a volume of 100 cm³ were installed horizontally under an undisturbed edge of the pit. Samples were dried at 105°C for 48 h and weighed. Soil bulk density was calculated as the fine earth mass over a known volume.

2.4. Soil OC and OM fractionation

Soil sampling was conducted on 2023–08–17 after the harvest of winter wheat and before the incorporation of stubble. In each of the 16 plots under 100 % rainfall, ten soil cores from 0 to 90 cm depth were taken with a mechanical auger and separated to 10 cm intervals. Soil cores from each depth interval were pooled into a composite sample and placed in air-tight sampling bags. In the lab, aliquots of 100 g were weighed and dried at 105°C for 48 h for gravimetric soil water content (SWC) determination. The remaining soil was air-dried at 20°C for 48 h and then, thoroughly mixed, sieved at 2 mm and ground.

Aliquots of air-dried, sieved and ground soil samples were taken for the determination of total soil C with an elemental analyzer (Vario MAX Cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany), according to DIN ISO 10694:1996–08. Separate aliquots were exposed to 450°C for 16 h to thermally decompose soil OM and, then, used for the determination of soil inorganic C with the elemental analyzer. As soil samples were free of inorganic C, SOC was equal to total C. This procedure was performed in duplicates and subsequent averaging for each sample. Water content remaining after air-drying was determined by weighing and drying of aliquots at 105°C, and used for mass correction. Soil OC stocks were calculated using soil bulk density for each 10 cm depth interval (for depths from 60 to 90 cm, soil bulk density of 50–60 cm was used). Soil OM was fractionated into POM and MAOM using the *by-size* fractionation method (Leuthold et al., 2022). We calculated the C content of each fraction in soil (units of %, or g fraction-C 100 g soil⁻¹) as the product of fraction percentage in soil and fraction C contents.

2.5. Soil water content NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻ and DOC

Soil ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) were monitored from 2022–11–01 to 2025–03–10. In plots without rainout shelters, soil samples were taken biweekly, with 80 sampling dates over this period. In plots with rainout shelters, soil sampling was done only 4 times in 2023, 6 times in 2024 and once in 2025. Sampling always coincided with flux measurements. At every sampling event, six soil samples at 0–30 cm soil depth were taken with a hand-driven auger (Ø 1 cm), placed in pre-labeled sampling bags and stored in cool-boxes until reaching the lab, where stored at –20°C. Al-

iquots from these samples were used for gravimetric water content. Soil NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ contents were determined after extraction with 0.01 M CaCl₂ in a ratio 1:2.5 and filtration, with a continuous flow analyzer with the AA3 auto-analyzer (following protocols by Seal Analytical GmbH, Norderstedt, Germany). Soil DOC content was determined after extraction with pure water, centrifugation and filtration (Guigue et al., 2014), with a Multi N/C 2100S (Analytik Jena, Jena).

2.6. Soil CO₂ and N₂O flux measurements

Soil CO₂ efflux, as a proxy for soil respiration, was monitored using rings (Ø 10 cm) permanently inserted into the soil to a depth of 1–2 cm, with an EGM-5 analyzer and SRC-2 chamber (PP Systems, Amesbury, USA). The dry CO₂ concentration was recorded for an observation time of 150 s with an initial dead-band of 30 s. Soil CO₂ efflux rates were calculated from the slope of the linear regression of dry CO₂ concentration over time. Rings were removed prior to soil management and reinstalled soon after.

Soil N₂O flux was monitored using rings (Ø 60 cm) permanently inserted into the soil to a depth of 1–2 cm with an LI7820 N₂O/H₂O analyzer (LI-COR Environmental, Nebraska, U.S.A.) and a custom-made static chamber (Kong et al., 2025; Pavelka et al., 2018). The chamber featured a large opening (Ø 4 cm) that was blocked with a stopper after installation over the ring to avoid building overpressure during chamber closure. In addition, the chamber was equipped with a small tube (Ø 4 mm and 25 cm long) passing through the chamber which remained open during measurements to avoid pressure built-up. Inside the chamber, a battery-powered fan was installed to support headspace homogeneity. Headspace temperature at starting and ending points were recorded with a thermometer passing through the chamber's sealing. The headspace temperature was used to correct for temperature induced gas volume changes. The dry N₂O concentration was recorded for 330 s with an initial dead-band of 30 s. Soil N₂O flux rates were calculated as the linear slope of dry N₂O concentration over time.

At every flux sampling event, soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes were measured once in each of the 16 plots, leading to four replicated measurements for each treatment combination. Fluxes were monitored for two successive years, from 2023–02–20 to 2025–03–10. Over this period, we measured fluxes on 135 dates. Fluxes were measured between 08:30 and 11:00 in the morning, as this time frame is assumed to represent mean daily flux rates (Ferrari Machado et al., 2019). Cumulative fluxes were calculated by linearly interpolating the fluxes between the measurement dates, and integration.

Each flux measurement was accompanied by soil temperature and volumetric SWC measurements (STP-2 thermometer, PP Systems, Amesbury, U.S.A. and Fieldscout TDR-350, Spectrum Technologies, Weiz, Austria, respectively) at 0–10 cm depth and close to the ring for N₂O measurements. Water-filled pore space (WFPS) was calculated using volumetric SWC and soil bulk density at 0–10 cm assuming a particle density of 2.65 g cm⁻³.

2.7. Data analysis

All data analysis was performed in R (R Core Team, 2024). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's Honest Significance Difference test were used to assess differences in soil parameters and cumulative fluxes, while the Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test was used to assess differences in crop biomass, using the *stats* package. The *caTools* package (Tuszynski, 2021) was used to perform linear interpolation for cumulative flux calculation. We used *lme4* (Bates et al., 2015) to perform linear mixed effects analysis of the relationship between soil GHG flux and tillage practices and rainfall percentage. Tillage practices, rainfall percentage, WFPS and soil temperature at 0–10 cm were included as fixed effects, with an interaction term between tillage practices and rainfall percentage. As random effects, we included intercepts for blocks and plots

nested in blocks, while we did not consider random slopes. We included a random intercept for dates to account for temporal autocorrelation. Continuous explanatory variables were always scaled. We visually inspected residual plots using *performance* (Lüdecke et al., 2021) to examine deviations from homoscedasticity and normality as well as the presence of outliers. When needed, we applied square-root, logarithmic or Box-Cox transformation on the response variable using *MASS* (Venables and Ripley, 2002), we removed outliers, and repeated the modeling steps. Null, full and selected models for each response variable are given in Table S3, together with their Akaike and Bayesian Information Criterion values and transformation λ -values. Following the same approach, we developed models for soil temperature and WFPS at 0–10 cm as well as for gravimetric SWC, soil NH_4 , NO_3 and DOC stocks at 0–30 cm. Contrasted comparisons were performed using *emmeans* (Lenth, 2024).

3. Results

3.1. Crop biomass and yield

The grain yield and stubble biomass of winter wheat did not differ between tillage practices or rainfall treatments (Fig. 1). The grain yield of winter barley under 100 % rainfall was $0.67 \pm 0.03 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$ in CT plots which was significantly higher than the $0.53 \pm 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$ in RT plots (Fig. 1A), but stubble biomass did not differ between tillage practices (Fig. 1B). Cover crop biomass did not differ between CT ($0.25 \pm 0.03 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) and RT ($0.22 \pm 0.04 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$) plots. Grain C and N did not differ between tillage practices or rainfall treatments (Fig. S3), while stubble C of winter wheat was higher in CT than in RT plots under 100 % rainfall.

3.2. Soil bulk density and OC stocks

Soil bulk density exhibited significant differences between CT and RT practices after 53 years (Fig. 2A). At 0–10 cm, CT plots had a soil bulk density of $1.33 \pm 0.03 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ which was higher than the $1.17 \pm 0.06 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ of RT plots. In contrast, at 10–20 cm, CT plots had a soil bulk density of $1.31 \pm 0.04 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ which was lower than the 1.43

$\pm 0.03 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ in RT plots. From 20–60 cm soil depth, soil bulk density did not differ between tillage practices.

After 53 years, CT led to a well-mixed ploughing layer (i.e., upper 27–30 cm), while RT resulted in a pronounced stratification of SOC contents and stocks (Fig. 2B, Table S5). At 0–10 cm, SOC stock in CT plots was $1.54 \pm 0.06 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$, which was significantly lower than the $1.93 \pm 0.09 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$ in RT plots. At 10–20 cm, CT and RT plots had similar SOC stocks, with 1.54 ± 0.15 and $1.55 \pm 0.13 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$, respectively. Interestingly, at 20–30 cm, SOC stock in CT plots was $1.58 \pm 0.16 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$, which was significantly higher than the $1.16 \pm 0.11 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$ in RT plots. Below 30 cm, CT and RT plots had similar SOC stocks. Cumulative SOC stocks at 0–30 cm, 0–60 cm and 0–90 cm depth did not differ between CT and RT plots (Fig. 4C).

The C content of OM fractions in soil differed significantly between tillage practices in the plough layer. At 0–10 cm, CT plots had lower POM-C content in soil than RT plots, while the opposite was found at 10–20 cm and 20–30 cm (Fig. 3A). Mineral-associated OM-C content in soil showed similar differences between tillage practices (Fig. 3B), with the exception of 10–20 cm layer where the two treatments did not differ. Despite this, the contribution of MAOM-C content in soil to bulk SOC at 10–30 cm was higher in RT than CT plots (Fig. 3C). In general, the contribution of MAOM-C in bulk SOC was higher than that of POM-C, and increased with depth.

3.3. Gravimetric SWC, soil mineral N and DOC

Over the study period, gravimetric SWC at 0–30 cm did not differ between tillage practices and averaged $20.7 \pm 0.3 \%$ and $20.4 \pm 0.2 \%$ in CT and RT plots, respectively, under 100 % rainfall (Table 1). The temporal variability of gravimetric SWC indicated that spring 2023 was much drier than spring 2024 (Fig. 4A). While tillage practice was selected in the mixed effects model for gravimetric SWC (Table S3, S4), its effect was not significant (Table S7, p-value = 0.060, which is < 0.100 , often referred to as marginally significant). Soil NH_4^+ stocks at 0–30 cm averaged $0.76 \pm 0.04 \text{ g N m}^{-2}$ in CT plots over the study period under 100 % rainfall, which was significantly higher than the $0.57 \pm 0.04 \text{ g N m}^{-2}$ in RT plots (Table 1). Soil NH_4^+ remained low throughout the study

Fig. 1. Grain yield (A) and stubble biomass (B) under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices and under ambient rainfall (100 %) and rainfall exclusion (50 %) in 2023 and 2024. Error bars indicate standard errors. Sample size is shown at the base of each bar. Upper-case letters indicate significant differences between tillage practices at p-value < 0.050.

Fig. 2. Soil bulk density (A) and soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks (B) at 10 cm depth intervals down to 90 cm, as well as cumulative SOC stocks at 0–30 cm, 0–60 cm and 0–90 cm (C) under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices. Error bars indicate standard errors with $n = 6$ for soil bulk density and standard deviation with $n = 8$ for SOC content and stocks. Asterisks indicate significant differences between tillage practices at p -value < 0.050 .

Fig. 3. Carbon content in soil of (A) particulate organic matter (POM) and (B) mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM), as well as (C) MAOM-C to bulk SOC ratio at 10 cm depth intervals down to 90 cm under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices. Error bars indicate standard errors with $n = 8$. Asterisks indicate significant differences between tillage practices at p -value < 0.050 .

period except for the weeks after fertilization (Fig. 4B). Tillage practice was a significant predictor of soil NH_4^+ (Table S4), and the higher stocks in CT compared to RT plots were also confirmed by our mixed effects analysis (Table S7). Similarly, soil NO_3^- stocks at 0–30 cm averaged 1.80 ± 0.15 g N m⁻² in CT plots, which was significantly higher than the 1.35 ± 0.05 g N m⁻² in RT plots under 100 % rainfall (Table 1). In contrast to soil NH_4^+ , soil NO_3^- stocks were more dynamic throughout the year and influenced by fertilization, stubble incorporation and tillage events (Fig. 4C). Tillage practice had a significant effect on soil NO_3^- in our mixed effects model (Table S4) with CT plots exhibiting higher stocks than RT plots (Table S7). Dissolved OC stocks did not differ between tillage practices (Table S4) and averaged 17.2 ± 0.8 g m⁻² in CT plots and 17.4 ± 0.3 g m⁻² in RT plots (Table 1). Based on sparse data, rainfall exclusion did not seem to affect gravimetric SWC, soil NH_4^+ and NO_3^- stocks or soil DOC at 0–30 cm (Fig. 4).

3.4. Soil temperature, moisture and CO₂ and N₂O fluxes

In general, WFPS at 0–10 cm (Fig. 5A) followed the pattern of gravimetric SWC at 0–30 cm (Fig. 4A). However, in contrast to

gravimetric SWC at 0–30 cm layer, WFPS at 0–10 cm was strongly influenced by tillage practice (Table S4). Differences in average WFPS between tillage practices were significant both under 100 % and 50 % rainfall over the total study period (Table 2) as well as, under 50 % rainfall, in the fallow 2024 period and in the cover crop period. Rainfall exclusion significantly reduced WFPS both in CT and RT plots over the total study period as well as during the individual crop and fallow periods (Table 2). Tillage practice and rainfall percentage were important predictors of WFPS in our mixed effects models (Table S4, S7).

Average soil temperature did not differ between tillage practices, while rainfall percentage led to significant differences only in RT plots, where plots under 100 % rainfall had lower soil temperature than plots under 50 % rainfall (Table 2). This was observed over the total study period as well as in the fallow 2024 period and during the cover crop period. These results were confirmed by our mixed effects analysis (Table S4, S7).

Soil CO₂ efflux was, in general, low during the winter months and increased in the spring and autumn months in every study year (Fig. 5C). During summer months, soil CO₂ efflux was higher than in the winter months but still relatively low and related to water availability. Agricultural management activities had a strong impact on soil CO₂ efflux,

Table 1

Gravimetric soil water content (SWC), soil NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) stocks at 0–30 cm as mean values (\pm standard error) over crop periods and the total study period under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices under 100 % rainfall percentage. Upper-case letters indicate significant differences between tillage practices at p -value < 0.050.

Crop/ Period (n days)	Tillage practice	Grav. SWC (%)	Soil NH_4 -N stock (g N m ⁻²)	Soil NO_3 -N stock (g N m ⁻²)	Soil DOC stock (g C m ⁻²)		
Winter wheat							
2022–23 (36)	CT	18.9 \pm 0.2	1.05 \pm 0.05	A	1.84 \pm 0.21	A	17.7 \pm 0.7
	RT	19.1 \pm 0.2	0.76 \pm 0.07	B	1.17 \pm 0.09	B	18.4 \pm 0.4
Fallow							
2023 (2)	CT	18.7 \pm 0.6	0.18 \pm 0.02		2.57 \pm 0.25		11.7 \pm 0.8
	RT	18.4 \pm 0.4	0.19 \pm 0.02		2.37 \pm 0.23		12.2 \pm 0.6
Winter barley							
2023–24 (25)	CT	22.4 \pm 0.4	0.73 \pm 0.06		1.45 \pm 0.10		17.0 \pm 1.0
	RT	21.4 \pm 0.3	0.56 \pm 0.05		1.45 \pm 0.02		16.1 \pm 0.3
Fallow							
2024 (5)	CT	21.8 \pm 0.4	0.18 \pm 0.02	A	2.45 \pm 0.27	A	-
	RT	19.8 \pm 0.3	0.16 \pm 0.01	B	1.62 \pm 0.07	B	-
Cover crop							
2024–25 (10)	CT	22.4 \pm 0.5	0.17 \pm 0.02		2.02 \pm 0.10		-
	RT	22.9 \pm 0.2	0.17 \pm 0.02		1.34 \pm 0.05		-
Whole period							
2022–2025 (78)	CT	20.7 \pm 0.3	0.76 \pm 0.04	A	1.80 \pm 0.15	A	17.2 \pm 0.8
	RT	20.4 \pm 0.2	0.57 \pm 0.04	B	1.35 \pm 0.05	B	17.4 \pm 0.3

which spiked after fertilization, harvest and stubble incorporation as well as tillage events. Nitrous oxide fluxes were in general low throughout the study period but we observed large N_2O emissions after fertilization, harvest and stubble incorporation events (Fig. 5D). Tillage events also led to N_2O emission peaks, although these were less pronounced than those caused by other management events. A peak in soil CO_2 and N_2O fluxes after 2023–06–22 was triggered by a severe rainfall event following an almost 4-week long dry period (Fig. 5A). Nitrous oxide peaks in late January 2023 and 2024 were probably caused by freeze-thaw events but our sparse sampling in winter periods did not allow further investigation. At times of low soil mineral N (Fig. 4), we observed negative N_2O fluxes, even though of low absolute values.

We observed that cumulative soil CO_2 efflux was lower in RT than CT plots under 100 % rainfall, even though this was not significant. For example, over the study period, cumulative soil CO_2 efflux was 1.50 ± 0.1 kg CO_2 -C m⁻² in CT plots and 1.28 ± 0.1 kg CO_2 -C m⁻² in RT plots under 100 % rainfall (Table 2). The same was found for the winter wheat and winter barley periods, as well as for the fallow period in 2024. We also observed that 50 % rainfall exclusion seemed to result in higher soil CO_2 fluxes both under CT and RT, and cumulative fluxes were 1.62 ± 0.2 kg CO_2 -C m⁻² in CT plots and 1.56 ± 0.1 kg CO_2 -C m⁻² in RT plots (Table 2). Rainfall exclusion seemed to decrease the difference between the two tillage practices, but the difference was not statistically significant. Similar (not significant) trends were found in the winter barley period as well as the fallow periods of 2023 and 2024.

Over the study period, the cumulative N_2O flux was 322.8 ± 51.0 μ g N_2O -N m⁻² in CT plots and 375.3 ± 66.3 μ g N_2O -N m⁻² in RT plots under 100 % rainfall (Table 2). Despite the lack of significant differences, we observed a trend for higher N_2O fluxes in RT than CT plots. Interestingly, under 50 % rainfall exclusion, the difference in cumulative N_2O flux between the two tillage treatments was larger (295.7 ± 48.2 μ g N_2O -N m⁻² in CT plots and 418.1 ± 90.9 μ g N_2O -N m⁻² in RT plots, Table 2), even though it remained statistically not significant. This was found in the total study period as well as in every cropping period except for the cover crop period.

Mixed effects models for soil CO_2 and N_2O fluxes included WFPS and soil temperature at 0–10 cm as well as tillage practice but not rainfall percentage, while the model for soil N_2O flux also included soil CO_2 efflux as a predictor (Table S4). Soil CO_2 efflux was negatively associated with WFPS and positively with soil temperature (Table S4). Soil CO_2 efflux seemed to be lower in RT than in CT plots but tillage practice was not a significant predictor (p -value = 0.115, Table S7). Soil N_2O flux

was positively related to soil temperature, WFPS and soil CO_2 efflux (Table S4). Soil N_2O flux seemed to be higher in RT than in CT plots but tillage practice effect was not significant (Table S7, p -value = 0.074, which is < 0.100, often referred to as marginally significant).

4. Discussion

4.1. Tillage practice and rainfall exclusion effects on crop yield

Evidence from temperate and cool regions, or regions where water is not a limiting factor of primary production, suggest that reducing tillage intensity does not have a strong effect on crop yield (Angers et al., 1997; Arango and Rice, 2021; Dimassi et al., 2014; Klopp et al., 2024; van Balen et al., 2023). Based on an economic analysis, Pearsons et al. (2023) reported that adoption of RT does not affect the long-term profitability of organic or conventional cropping systems. In contrast, in a global meta-analysis, van Kessel et al. (2013) found that long-term conservation tillage (i.e., practices that reduce tillage intensity compared to conventional practices such as no-till and RT) were associated with lower yields than CT in humid regions, with an effect size of about -6 %. In Garte-Sued, we estimated a relative yield loss of 6.4 ± 1.8 % (average \pm stand. error from 39 archived harvest events, Table S2) under RT compared to CT which, however, was not statistically significant in line with our first hypothesis.

In this study, we observed that RT led to similar yield of winter wheat as CT but to lower yield of winter barley (Fig. 1). Investigating the archives of Garte-Sued, we found that spring and winter barley often produced lower yields under RT than CT (i.e., in five out of seven harvest events since 1970) exhibiting an average yield loss of 11.7 ± 4.9 % under RT. In contrast, spring and winter wheat usually produced similar yields under both tillage practices (i.e., in 11 out of 14 harvest events since 1970) and exhibited an average yield loss of 6.2 ± 1.7 % under RT, which matched the long-term relative yield loss of RT. This indicates that crop species, in addition to pedoclimatic conditions, can influence the effects of tillage practice on crop yield (as observed also by van Balen et al., 2023).

In contrast to our first hypothesis, rainfall exclusion did not significantly affect the yields of winter wheat or winter barley and did not lead to differences between tillage practices (Fig. 1), likely because our treatment did not induce water stress in the crops. Although rainfall exclusion substantially reduced soil moisture in the upper 10 cm (Fig. 5A, Table S4), soil moisture at 0–30 cm was similar between the

Fig. 4. Gravimetric soil water content (A), soil ammonium (NH_4^+) (B), soil nitrate (NO_3^-) (C) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) (D) stocks at 0–30 cm under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices and under ambient rainfall (100 %) and rainfall exclusion (50 %). Labels indicate cropping periods (i.e., Winter wheat, Winter barley and Cover crop mixture) with fallow periods in between. Dotted lines indicate management events (F: fertilization with load in $kg\ N\ ha^{-1}$, H: harvest, I: stubble incorporation, T: tillage, S: sowing).

100 % and 50 % rainfall treatments (Fig. S4A), suggesting that sufficient water remained available for crop development under the rainout shelters. We attribute this primarily to soil and site characteristics at Garte-Sued. First, Haplic Luvisols have an argillic horizon in the subsoil, which can impede drainage (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) and promote water retention in the rooting zone. Additionally, the elevation of the site (163–167 m above sea level) and its proximity (less than 400 m) to the Garte Stream (elevation 160 m) suggest a shallow groundwater table, which may further contribute to water supply of the rooting zone. Empirical observations indicate that Garte-Sued and surrounding fields are frequently waterlogged during late winter and early spring (i.e., in wet and cold periods, Fig. S1). Rainout shelters may have methodological limitations, as they showed to be more effective for moderating soil moisture by slowing the rewetting of dry soils or accelerating the drying of wet soils (Fig. 5A). However, they were less

effective during prolonged dry or wet periods occurring intra-annually and therefore might have influenced the yields.

4.2. Effects of reduced tillage on soil organic carbon

Agroecological practices aiming at CO_2 mitigation try to increase SOM stocks either by increasing OM inputs into the soil, or by reducing soil C losses (Chenu et al., 2019). While there is a consensus among scientists that increasing OM inputs is more effective when targeting CO_2 mitigation (Minasny et al., 2017), the issue remains that additional OM inputs must often be exported from other agroecosystems which might, therefore, suffer a SOM loss. In contrast, reducing C losses by minimizing disturbances, for example by reducing tillage intensity, has the merit of not relying on exogenous OM (Powlson et al., 2011). However, it has become clear in studies examining the ploughing layer

Fig. 5. Soil water-filled pore space (A), soil temperature (B), soil CO₂ efflux (C) and soil N₂O flux (D) under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices and under ambient rainfall (100 %) and rainfall exclusion (50 %). Labels indicate cropping periods (i.e., Winter wheat, Winter barley and Cover crop mixture) with fallow periods in between. Dotted lines indicate management events (F: fertilization with load in kg N ha⁻¹, H: harvest, I: stubble incorporation, T: tillage, S: sowing).

and the subsoil underneath that reducing tillage intensity does not result in a net SOC stock increase under temperate climates, or in regions where water is not a limiting factor of primary production (Angers et al., 1997; Haddaway et al., 2017; Minasny et al., 2017). In agreement with our second hypothesis, our study confirms that reducing tillage intensity does not lead to greater SOC stocks than CT in temperate, medium-textured soils even after long implementation periods (here 53 years) (Fig. 2C). This is in line with studies conducted on Luvisols and temperate climates similar to our study (Dimassi et al., 2014; Feng et al., 2025; Stockfisch et al., 1999; Tobiášová et al., 2023).

Conventional tillage practices mix plant residues within the whole ploughing layer leading to an evenly distributed SOM (Baker et al., 2007; Dimassi et al., 2014; Staley et al., 1988). In contrast, limiting soil management to a shallower depth, as it is done in RT practices, incorporates plant residues in the uppermost soil causing stratification of

SOM. In line with our second hypothesis, we also observed a well-mixed ploughing layer in CT plots (Fig. 2B), while RT led to OM accumulation in the harrowing layer (i.e., 0–10 cm) and OM loss deeper in the ploughing layer (i.e., 20–30 cm). Even though this OM redistribution did not lead to a net SOC stock increase (Fig. 2C), it might still be biogeochemically relevant for climate change as: i) tillage practice might also influence the relative distribution of POM and MAOM (Panagea et al., 2022; Prairie et al., 2023), which have distinct decomposability (Yu et al., 2022), and ii) accumulation of OM in biologically active soil layers can potentially influence N cycling and trigger soil N₂O emissions (Haas et al., 2022; Lugato et al., 2018; Stuchiner et al., 2024; Surey et al., 2020).

The Garte-Sued field trial on tillage practices started in 1970. Soil OC stocks at 0–30 cm were 3.92 kg m⁻² under CT and 4.33 kg m⁻² under RT practice 25 years after the initiation of the trial (soil sampling in

Table 2

Soil temperature and water-filled pore space (WFPS) at 0–10 cm as well as cumulative soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes as mean values (\pm standard error) over crop periods and the total study period under conventional tillage (CT) and reduced tillage (RT) practices and under 100 % and 50 % rainfall percentage. Upper-case letters indicate significant differences between tillage practices and lower-case letters between rainfall treatments at p-value < 0.050.

Crop/ Period (n days)	Tillage practice	Rainfall percentage	Average soil temperature (°C)		Average WFPS (%)		Cumulative CO ₂ flux (g CO ₂ -C m ⁻²)	Cumulative N ₂ O flux (mg N ₂ O-N m ⁻²)
Winter wheat 2022–23 (47)	CT	100 %	11.1 \pm 0.3		45.3 \pm 0.5	a	449.7 \pm 28.0	30.6 \pm 12.5
		50 %	10.9 \pm 0.1		42.2 \pm 0.8	a	381.9 \pm 48.6	17.4 \pm 4.1
	RT	100 %	10.8 \pm 0.1		45.1 \pm 1.2	a	338.9 \pm 26.3	41.9 \pm 7.0
		50 %	11.0 \pm 0.2		41.2 \pm 0.8	b	383.2 \pm 8.6	44.7 \pm 8.8
Fallow 2023 (10)	CT	100 %	17.3 \pm 0.1	a	48.4 \pm 2.4	a	140.1 \pm 16.9	19.1 \pm 3.2
		50 %	18.4 \pm 0.2	b	31.3 \pm 1.9	b	172.9 \pm 7.3	14.9 \pm 3.4
	RT	100 %	17.3 \pm 0.1	a	44.5 \pm 2.9	a	145.6 \pm 13.7	28.7 \pm 8.8
		50 %	18.8 \pm 0.2	b	30.8 \pm 2.7	b	163.4 \pm 4.0	33.3 \pm 11.5
Winter barley 2023–24 (55)	CT	100 %	10.0 \pm 0.1		58.3 \pm 0.2	a	359.9 \pm 45.0	76.7 \pm 17.8
		50 %	10.1 \pm 0.0		46.2 \pm 1.3	b	491.4 \pm 86.8	67.4 \pm 11.6
	RT	100 %	10.1 \pm 0.0		54.7 \pm 0.8	a	300.6 \pm 54.5	152.5 \pm 51.0
		50 %	10.3 \pm 0.1		43.6 \pm 0.5	b	434.0 \pm 71.0	140.7 \pm 51.6
Fallow 2024 (10)	CT	100 %	18.4 \pm 0.1	a	62.3 \pm 0.8	a	190.6 \pm 30.5	71.9 \pm 13.2
		50 %	18.9 \pm 0.1	b	37.4 \pm 3.8	Ab	225.4 \pm 39.0	40.4 \pm 11.3
	RT	100 %	18.2 \pm 0.1	a	50.5 \pm 1.7	a	149.8 \pm 11.1	58.5 \pm 9.5
		50 %	19.0 \pm 0.2	b	26.8 \pm 1.1	Bb	263.2 \pm 42.1	78.4 \pm 36.1
Cover crop 2024–25 (15)	CT	100 %	10.9 \pm 0.0	a	56.4 \pm 0.6	a	278.9 \pm 65.5	71.6 \pm 19.4
		50 %	11.3 \pm 0.1	b	48.4 \pm 2.0	Ab	242.8 \pm 74.6	99.5 \pm 7.9
	RT	100 %	11.1 \pm 0.0	a	51.8 \pm 0.9	a	258.3 \pm 45.2	38.5 \pm 12.4
		50 %	11.4 \pm 0.1	b	38.5 \pm 2.3	Bb	234.7 \pm 33.7	79.7 \pm 11.5
Study period 2022–2025 (135)	CT	100 %	11.5 \pm 0.2		53.1 \pm 0.5	Aa	1501.2 \pm 126.4	322.8 \pm 51.0
		50 %	11.7 \pm 0.1		43.6 \pm 0.8	Ab	1618.2 \pm 236.3	295.7 \pm 48.2
	RT	100 %	11.4 \pm 0.1	a	50.0 \pm 1.1	Ba	1284.7 \pm 97.9	375.3 \pm 66.3
		50 %	11.9 \pm 0.1	b	40.1 \pm 0.5	Bb	1560.3 \pm 137.2	418.1 \pm 90.9

1995, Reiter et al., 2002a) and 3.70 kg m⁻² in CT and 3.90 kg m⁻² in RT 37 years after the initiation of the trial (soil sampling in 2007, Heinze et al., 2010). In this study, we found that SOC stocks at 0–30 cm were 4.66 \pm 0.34 kg m⁻² under CT and 4.65 \pm 0.29 kg m⁻² under RT practice 53 years after the initiation of the trial (soil sampling in 2023, Fig. 2C). Soil OC stocks were similar under CT and RT between 25 and 53 years after the initiation of the trial. Differences over the years are probably related to the timing of the sampling (e.g., pre and post stubble incorporation, Stockfisch et al., 1999). Unfortunately, we were not able to retrieve data on SOC content or stocks from the initial stages of the trial. For this reason, we make no claims on C sequestration (Don et al., 2024) but, rather, we discuss SOC stocks differences between tillage practices at a given point in time.

The relative importance of POM and MAOM fractions for C sequestration and climate change mitigation remains a point of discussion. Mineral-associated OM has greater resistance to decomposition compared to POM, making it particularly relevant for long-term C storage (Lavallee et al., 2020). However, POM acts as the primary precursor of MAOM (Witzgall et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022). Thus, agroecological practices that lead to POM accumulation in the short term may promote MAOM formation in the long-term. In our study, by incorporating plant residues in the upper 7–10 cm of soil, RT led to a significant accumulation of POM and POM-C in the uppermost soil compared to CT (Fig. 3A, Table S6). We assume that, in time, this POM accumulation resulted in the significant MAOM-C accumulation observed in the same depth (Fig. 3B). However, below the harrowing layer, both POM and MAOM were lower under RT than under CT after 53 years of implementation. This suggests that reducing tillage intensity has a limited potential for MAOM formation in temperate, medium-textured soils even after long implementation periods.

4.3. Reduced tillage and rainfall exclusion effects on CO₂ and N₂O fluxes

Reducing tillage intensity has been linked to negative, neutral or positive effects on N₂O emissions. In recent meta-analyses, Grados et al. (2022) reported a marginal increase in N₂O emissions under no-till and RT compared to CT, while Mei et al. (2018) found higher N₂O emissions under no-till but not under RT compared to CT. When focusing on cool temperate climates, N₂O emissions under both conservation tillage practices were similar to CT. Yao et al. (2024) found no differences in yield-scaled N₂O emissions under no-till, RT and CT for three grain crops and, similarly, van Kessel et al. (2013) found no differences in area- or yield-scaled N₂O emissions under no-till, RT and CT in a meta-analysis on humid climates. These discrepancies may derive from the influence of pedoclimatic conditions on the effects of tillage practice on N cycling, the inherently high variability of N₂O fluxes and the relatively low statistical power of most studies (Kim et al., 2025). In this study, we observed a trend for higher N₂O emissions under RT than CT (Table S4, S7) partially in line with our third hypothesis. The large spatial and temporal variability of the fluxes may have, at least partially, contributed to the lack of statistical significance.

Tillage practices can influence water availability and soil aeration, which in turn regulate the balance between aerobic and anaerobic conditions, as well as the availability of labile OM and N, thereby affecting soil N₂O production and release. For example, practices that reduce tillage intensity can enhance soil water retention (like no-till, Abid and Lal, 2009), potentially increasing the formation of anaerobic microsites. This may promote denitrification and N₂O production compared to CT, particularly in fine- and medium-textured soils under no-till (Ma et al., 2013; Rochette et al., 2008) or under dry climates (Linn and Doran, 1984), but it could also lower N₂O emissions if complete denitrification to N₂ is favored. In addition, long-term no-till and RT have been found to improve pore connectivity compared to CT (Pagliai

et al., 2004; Pires et al., 2017), which might promote N₂O emissions due to better gas diffusivity. In this study, we observed that N₂O fluxes were positively related to soil moisture (Table S4), which was slightly lower under RT than under CT in the topsoil (at 0–10 cm, p-value = 0.004, and at 0–30 cm, p-value = 0.060, Table S7). The slightly lower soil moisture under RT than CT, together with a lower uppermost soil bulk density (in our study, Fig. 2A, but also in other Haplic Luvisols, Stockfisch et al., 1999), might have sustained enough anaerobic microsites to produce N₂O via denitrification while allowing for its release to the atmosphere before further reduction to N₂.

Soil N availability is a primary driver of soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes (Kim et al., 2025; Nasser et al., 2025), and it is largely determined by N inputs through fertilization. In our study, N fertilization events led to peaks in soil mineral N (Fig. 4 B, C), accompanied by peaks in N₂O fluxes (Fig. 5D). However, the third fertilization event of winter wheat (2023–05–22, 61 kg N ha⁻¹ as ammonium nitrate-urea solution, Table S1) did not lead to an immediate peak of N₂O fluxes (Fig. 5D), which could be attributed to low soil moisture (Figs. 4A, 5A). Pelster et al. (2021) also reported an asynchrony between soil mineral N and N₂O emissions after fertilization events, with soil mineral N peaking shortly after fertilization, while N₂O emissions peaked when a rainfall event led to WFPS > 60 % in the following week. Similarly, in our study, soil N₂O (and CO₂) fluxes peaked about four weeks after the third fertilization event of winter wheat, when an intense rainfall occurred (on 2023–06–22; approximately 37 mm in less than 24 h). However, as soil mineral N only exhibited a small response to this fertilization event (Fig. 4B, C), we think that the dense canopy of winter wheat at the time of the event (no data available) might have intercepted a portion of the liquid fertilization applied.

Apart from N fertilization, management activities like harvest, stubble incorporation and tillage events also influence soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes (D'Amours et al., 2023; Kesenheimer et al., 2019; Nasser et al., 2025) due to OM input and soil mixing. In our study, we observed that soil CO₂ and N₂O peaked after harvest and stubble incorporation but peaks after tillage events were less pronounced (Fig. 5). Interestingly, soil NH₄⁺ was not affected while soil NO₃⁻ increased after harvest, stubble incorporation and tillage events (Fig. 4B, C). This likely indicates that CO₂ and N₂O peaks occurred due to increased OM mineralization and nitrification under high C and N availability and favorable soil temperature and moisture conditions (Pelster et al., 2021), which is supported by a positive relationship between soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes in our study (Table S4). However, labile OM inputs can also result in N₂O emissions via denitrification due to the consumption of oxygen during OM mineralization and the creation of anaerobic microsites (Rummel et al., 2020).

Increased topsoil OM under no-till compared to CT is often attributed to greater biomass C inputs into the soil (Virto et al., 2012). Other studies, however, observed similar crop stubble biomass between tillage practices (Dimassi et al., 2014) and suggested that differences in soil C dynamics between tillage practices were not explained by OM inputs. In Garte-Sued, litter decomposition has been found to be faster in CT than under RT throughout the ploughing layer (Jacobs et al., 2011). In this study, we did not observe differences in the stubble biomass of winter wheat or winter barley between tillage practices (Fig. 1B) and, while there was a tendency for lower soil CO₂ efflux under RT compared to CT (even though not significant, Table 2, S4), it did not result in greater SOC under RT (Fig. 2C). In contrast to what was proposed in recent studies (Stuchiner et al., 2024; Surey et al., 2020), SOC as well as POM-C and MAOM-C were not related to soil N₂O fluxes (correlation not shown).

Crops can also influence soil N₂O fluxes via N uptake and OM inputs (Rummel et al., 2021), and tillage practice effects on soil N₂O fluxes might be mediated, at least partially, by these mechanisms. Arango and Rice (2021) did not observe differences in N uptake rates of corn under no-till and CT, while Volpi et al. (2020) observed higher N uptake under RT compared to CT for sunflower but not for durum wheat. A study

conducted at Garte-Sued determined lower soil N uptake under RT than CT for two leguminous crops (Reiter et al., 2002b). Even though we did not measure soil N uptake rates over the growing period, we observed similar grain and stubble biomass N in winter wheat and winter barley between tillage practices (Fig. S4C, D), suggesting similar cumulative soil N uptakes. Therefore, the slightly higher soil N₂O fluxes we observed under RT were probably not explained by crop N uptake.

Soil mineral N in the topsoil was higher under CT than under RT (Table 1, S4) despite the equal N additions between tillage practices in our study. This agrees with studies conducted in humid temperate Haplic Luvisols (Feng et al., 2025) and, in Garte-Sued, it could be attributed to higher litter decomposition rates and higher N mineralization rates observed under CT than RT (Jacobs et al., 2011; Reiter, 2002b). Soil NO₃⁻ stocks were strongly and positively associated with soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes, and this relationship was not affected by tillage practice (Fig. S5). However, despite the positive relationship between soil NO₃⁻ stocks and soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes, the higher soil NO₃⁻ under CT than RT did not result in higher soil CO₂ and N₂O fluxes (Table S7).

Low soil respiration in agricultural soils as a result of dry conditions due to reduced rainfall is documented both in observational and experimental studies (Apostolakis et al., 2022; Leyrer et al., 2025). In arable soils, soil CO₂ efflux was higher under no-till than CT during a growing season with less than normal rainfall, which was attributed to a higher WFPS (Venterea et al., 2006). In our study, we observed that RT was associated with lower cumulative soil CO₂ fluxes than CT and that 50 % rainfall exclusion seemed to close the gap between the two tillage practices, however these differences were not statistically significant (Table 2). In contrast, 50 % rainfall exclusion seemed to enhance the difference in cumulative N₂O fluxes between tillage practices as it decreased N₂O fluxes under CT and increased N₂O fluxes under RT but again these differences were not statistically significant (Table 2). The lack of a more pronounced effect from 50 % rainfall exclusion on GHG fluxes was likely because rainfall exclusion resulted in reduced soil moisture only in the uppermost 10 cm of soil (Table 2) but not deeper (Table 1, Fig. S4A). However, over time, soil N₂O fluxes were significantly and positively associated with WFPS at 0–10 cm of soil (t-value = 5.983, Table S4), which might indicate that a uniform reduction in rainfall, without changes in its intra-annual distribution, would potentially reduce soil N₂O fluxes (Gelfand et al., 2015). In this study, although not significant, we observed larger N₂O fluxes under RT than under CT under reduced rainfall (Table 2). This suggests that under drier conditions, the selection of tillage practice might play a more relevant role for climate change mitigation, and that in medium-textured soils under humid temperate climates, RT might not be a desirable practice for climate change mitigation.

5. Conclusions

After 53 years of continuous management, the Garte-Sued field trial demonstrated that RT leads to a pronounced stratification of SOC, with greater SOC and POM accumulation in the upper 10 cm of soil compared to CT. However, these differences in SOC distribution did not lead to higher SOC stocks at 0–90 cm. Crop yields were, in general, lower under RT compared to CT but the significance of the effect depended on crop species. Reduced rainfall (via rainfall exclusion) did not significantly affect crop yields or cumulative GHG fluxes, likely due to the inherent water retention capacity of the soil and the moderate level of imposed water deficit. In cumulative terms, RT tended to decrease soil CO₂ fluxes and to increase N₂O fluxes relative to CT, even though not significantly. Reduced rainfall tended to enhance the difference in cumulative N₂O emissions between tillage practices. The findings suggest that, in medium-textured soils under humid temperate climates, RT does not offer benefits in terms of crop yield, SOC stocks or GHG emission mitigation, and it has the potential to increase GHG emissions under reduced rainfall.

Future research should prioritize the integration of multiple

agroecological practices, and the examination of their interactions with increasingly extreme climate stressors. Studies are needed that investigate the combined effects of practices designed to increase OM inputs to soils with those aiming at reducing OM losses. Such combined approaches may offer greater potential for enhancing SOC stocks and mitigate GHG emissions than single interventions alone. Moreover, in the context of emerging C farming schemes in the EU, it is important to investigate not only the effects of sustained agroecological practices across multiple aspects of agricultural systems, but also the consequences of discontinuing these practices after years of implementation. Understanding the durability and resilience of accrued benefits will be key for designing effective incentive structures and ensuring long-term climate and environmental benefits.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Antonios Apostolakis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Daka Oliver:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Paulina Englert:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Stefan Siebert:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Ana Meijide:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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Appendix A. Supporting information

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Abid, M., Lal, R. 2009. Tillage and drainage impact on soil quality: II. Tensile strength of aggregates, moisture retention and water infiltration. *Soil Tillage Res.* Contains

- papers from HighLand 2006: Land Degradation and Soil and Water Conservation in Tropical Highlands, Mekelle, Ethiopia, 21-25 September 2006 103, 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2008.11.004>.
- Ahl, C., Joergensen, R.G., Kandeler, E., Meyer, B., Woehler, V., 1998. Microbial biomass and activity in silt and sand loams after long-term shallow tillage in central Germany. *Soil Tillage Res.* 49, 93–104. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(98\)00166-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(98)00166-4).
- Angers, D.A., Bolinder, M.A., Carter, M.R., Gregorich, E.G., Drury, C.F., Liang, B.C., Voroney, R.P., Simard, R.R., Donald, R.G., Beyaert, R.P., Martel, J., 1997. Impact of tillage practices on organic carbon and nitrogen storage in cool, humid soils of eastern Canada. *Soil Tillage Res. Soil Biol. Tillage* 41, 191–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(96\)01100-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(96)01100-2).
- Apostolakis, A., Panakoulia, S., Nikolaidis, N.P., Paranychianakis, N.V., 2017. Shifts in soil structure and soil organic matter in a chronosequence of set-aside fields. *Soil Tillage Res.* 174, 113–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2017.07.004>.
- Apostolakis, A., Schöning, I., Michalzik, B., Klaus, V.H., Boeddinghaus, R.S., Kandeler, E., Marhan, S., Bolliger, R., Fischer, M., Prati, D., Hänsel, F., Naus, T., Hölzel, N., Kleinebecker, T., Schrupp, M., 2022. Drivers of soil respiration across a management intensity gradient in temperate grasslands under drought. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosys.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-022-10224-2>.
- Arango, M.A., Rice, C.W., 2021. Impact of nitrogen management and tillage practices on nitrous oxide emissions from rainfed corn. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 85, 1425–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1002/saj2.20285>.
- Baker, J.M., Ochsner, T.E., Venterea, R.T., Griffis, T.J., 2007. Tillage and soil carbon sequestration—What do we really know? *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 118 (1–4), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2006.05.014>.
- Bates, D., Maechler, M., Bolker, B., Walker, S., 2015. Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *J. Stat. Softw.* 67 (1), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>.
- Bavin, T.K., Griffis, T.J., Baker, J.M., Venterea, R.T., 2009. Impact of reduced tillage and cover cropping on the greenhouse gas budget of a maize/soybean rotation ecosystem. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 134, 234–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2009.07.005>.
- Chenu, C., Angers, D.A., Barré, P., Derrien, D., Arrouays, D., Balesdent, J., 2019. Increasing organic stocks in agricultural soils: Knowledge gaps and potential innovations. *Soil Tillage Res.* 188, 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2018.04.011>.
- D’Amours, J., Pelster, D.E., Gagné, G., Wilkinson, J.A., Chantigny, M.H., Angers, D.A., Halde, C., 2023. Combining reduced tillage and green manures minimized N₂O emissions from organic cropping systems in a cool humid climate. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 341, 108205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108205>.
- Deutsches Institut für Normung, 1996. Soil quality – Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion (elementary analysis). DIN ISO 10694:1996-08. Beuth Verlag, Berlin.
- Dimassi, B., Mary, B., Wylleman, R., Labreuche, J., Couture, D., Piroux, F., Cohan, J.-P., 2014. Long-term effect of contrasted tillage and crop management on soil carbon dynamics during 41 years. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 188, 134–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.02.014>.
- Don, A., Seidel, F., Leifeld, J., Kätterer, T., Martin, M., Pellerin, S., Emde, D., Seitz, D., Chenu, C., 2024. Carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation—Definitions and pitfalls. *Glob. Change Biol.* 30, e16983. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16983>.
- Feng, W., Ai, J., Sánchez-Rodríguez, A.R., Li, S., Zhang, W., Yang, H., Apostolakis, A., Muentner, C., Li, F.-M., Dippold, M.A., Zhou, J., Dittert, K., Wang, H., 2025. Depth-dependent patterns in soil organic C, enzymatic stoichiometric ratio, and soil quality under conventional tillage and reduced tillage after 55-years. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 385, 109584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2025.109584>.
- Ferrari Machado, P.V., Wagner-Riddle, C., MacTavish, R., Voroney, P.R., Bruulsema, T. W., 2019. Diurnal variation and sampling frequency effects on nitrous oxide emissions following nitrogen fertilization and spring-thaw events. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 83, 743–750. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2018.10.0365>.
- Gelfand, I., Cui, M., Tang, J., Robertson, G.P., 2015. Short-term drought response of N₂O and CO₂ emissions from mesic agricultural soils in the US Midwest. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 212, 127–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2015.07.005>.
- Georgiou, K., Jackson, R.B., Vindušková, O., Abramoff, R.Z., Ahlström, A., Feng, W., Harden, J.W., Pellegrini, A.F.A., Polley, H.W., Soong, J.L., Riley, W.J., Torn, M.S., 2022. Global stocks and capacity of mineral-associated soil organic carbon. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 3797. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31540-9>.
- Grados, D., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Chen, J., Jan van Groenigen, K., Olesen, J.E., Willem van Groenigen, J., Abalos, D., 2022. Synthesizing the evidence of nitrous oxide mitigation practices in agroecosystems. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17, 114024. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac9b50>.
- Guigue, J., Mathieu, O., Lévêque, J., Mounier, S., Laffont, R., Maron, P.A., Navarro, N., Chateau, C., Amiotte-Suchet, P., Lucas, Y., 2014. A comparison of extraction procedures for water-extractable organic matter in soils. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 65, 520–530. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12156>.
- Haas, E., Carozzi, M., Massad, R.S., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Scheer, C., 2022. Long term impact of residue management on soil organic carbon stocks and nitrous oxide emissions from European croplands. *Sci. Total Environ.* 836, 154932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154932>.
- Haddaway, N.R., Hedlund, K., Jackson, L.E., Kätterer, T., Lugato, E., Thomsen, I.K., Joergensen, H.B., Isberg, P.-E., 2017. How does tillage intensity affect soil organic carbon? A systematic review. *Environ. Evid.* 6, 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-017-0108-9>.
- Heinze, S., Rauber, R., Joergensen, R.G., 2010. Influence of mouldboard plough and rotary harrow tillage on microbial biomass and nutrient stocks in two long-term

- experiments on loess derived Luvisols. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 46, 405–412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2010.09.011>.
- IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015. World Reference Base for Soil Resources 2014, update 2015. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. World Soil Resources Reports No. 106. FAO, Rome.
- Jacobs, A., Ludwig, B., Schmidt, J.H., Bergstermann, A., Rauber, R., Joergensen, R.G., 2011. Influence of tillage on degradation kinetics using the litterbag method. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 47, 198–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2010.11.011>.
- Jacobs, A., Rauber, R., Ludwig, B., 2009. Impact of reduced tillage on carbon and nitrogen storage of two Haplic Luvisols after 40 years. *Soil Tillage Res.* 102, 158–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2008.08.012>.
- Kesenheimer, K., Pandeya, H.R., Müller, T., Buegger, F., Ruser, R., 2019. Nitrous oxide emissions after incorporation of winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.) residues under two different tillage treatments. *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 182, 48–59. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.201700507>.
- van Kessel, C., Venterea, R., Six, J., Adviento-Borbe, M.A., Linquist, B., van Groenigen, K. J., 2013. Climate, duration, and N placement determine N₂O emissions in reduced tillage systems: a meta-analysis. *Glob. Change Biol.* 19, 33–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2012.02779.x>.
- Kim, N., Jang, C., Yang, W.H., Guan, K., DeLucia, E.H., Lee, D., 2025. Spatial variability of agricultural soil carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide fluxes: characterization and recommendations from spatially high-resolution, multi-year dataset. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 387, 109636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2025.109636>.
- Klopp, H.W., Blanco-Canqui, H., Creech, C.F., Easterly, A.C., 2024. Identifying the best tillage system to maintain soil properties and crop yields after conservation reserve program grassland conversion. *Soil Tillage Res.* 239, 106060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2024.106060>.
- Kong, M., Mitu, F.F., Petersen, S.O., Lærke, P.E., Abalos, D., Sørensen, P., Brændholt, A., Bruun, S., Eriksen, J., Dold, C., 2025. A comparison of chamber-based methods for measuring N₂O emissions from arable soils. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 370, 110591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2025.110591>.
- Kundel, D., Meyer, S., Birkhofer, H., Fliessbach, A., Mäder, P., Scheu, S., van Kleunen, M., Birkhofer, K., 2018. Design and manual to construct rainout-shelters for climate change experiments in agroecosystems. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 6.
- Lavallee, J.M., Soong, J.L., Cotrufo, M.F., 2020. Conceptualizing soil organic matter into particulate and mineral-associated forms to address global change in the 21st century. *Glob. Change Biol.* 26, 261–273. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14859>.
- Lenth, R., 2024. emmeans: Estimated marginal means, aka least-squares means. R package version 1.10.0. Available from: (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=emmeans>).
- Leuthold, S.J., Haddix, M.L., Lavallee, J.M., Cortufo, F.M., 2022. Physical fractionation techniques. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-822974-3.00067-7>.
- Leyrer, V., Blum, J., Marhan, S., Kandelner, E., Zimmermann, T., Berauer, B.J., Schweiger, A.H., Canarini, A., Richter, A., Poll, C., 2025. Drought impacts on plant-soil carbon allocation—integrating future mean climatic conditions. *Glob. Change Biol.* 31, e70070. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70070>.
- Li, C., Frolking, S., Butterbach-Bahl, K., 2005. Carbon sequestration in arable soils is likely to increase nitrous oxide emissions, offsetting reductions in climate radiative forcing. *Clim. Change* 72, 321–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-005-6791-5>.
- Linn, D.M., Doran, J.W., 1984. Effect of water-filled pore space on carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide production in tilled and nontilled soils. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 48, 1267–1272. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1984.03615995004800060013x>.
- Lüdecke, D., Ben-Shachar, M., Patil, I., Makowski, D., 2021. performance: an R package for assessment, comparison and testing of statistical models. *J. Open Source Softw.* 6 (60), 3139. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03139>.
- Lugato, E., Leip, A., Jones, A., 2018. Mitigation potential of soil carbon management overestimated by neglecting N₂O emissions. *Nat. Clim. Change* 8, 219–223. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0087-z>.
- Ma, Y., Sun, L., Zhang, X., Yang, B., Wang, J., Yin, B., Yan, X., Xiong, Z., 2013. Mitigation of nitrous oxide emissions from paddy soil under conventional and no-till practices using nitrification inhibitors during the winter wheat-growing season. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 49, 627–635. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-012-0753-7>.
- Mei, K., Wang, Z., Huang, H., Zhang, C., Shang, X., Dahlgren, R.A., Zhang, M., Xia, F., 2018. Stimulation of N₂O emission by conservation tillage management in agricultural lands: a meta-analysis. *Soil Tillage Res.* 182, 86–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2018.05.006>.
- Minasny, B., Malone, B.P., McBratney, A.B., Angers, D.A., Arrouays, D., Chambers, A., Chaplot, V., Chen, Z.-S., Cheng, K., Das, B.S., Field, D.J., Gimona, A., Hedley, C.B., Hong, S.Y., Mandal, B., Marchant, B.P., Martin, M., McConkey, B.G., Mulder, V.L., O'Rourke, S., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Odeh, I., Padarian, J., Paustian, K., Pan, G., Poggio, L., Savin, I., Stolbovov, V., Stockmann, U., Sulaeman, Y., Tsui, C.-C., Vágen, T.-G., van Wesemael, B., Winowicki, L., 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002>.
- Nasser, V., Dechow, R., Helfrich, M., Meijde, A., Rummel, P.S., Koch, H.-J., Ruser, R., Essich, L., Dittert, K., 2025. Evaluating N₂O emissions and carbon sequestration in temperate croplands with cover crops: insights from field trials. *SOIL* 11, 489–506. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-11-489-2025>.
- Newton, A.C., Guy, D.C., Bengough, A.G., Gordon, D.C., McKenzie, B.M., Sun, B., Valentine, T.A., Hallett, P.D., 2012. Soil tillage effects on the efficacy of cultivars and their mixtures in winter barley. *Field Crops Res.* 128, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2011.12.004>.
- Pagliai, M., Vignozzi, N., Pellegrini, S., 2004. Soil structure and the effect of management practices. *Soil Tillage Res. Soil Phys. Qual.* 79, 131–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2004.07.002>.
- Panagea, I.S., Apostolakis, A., Berti, A., Bussell, J., Čermak, P., Diels, J., Elsen, A., Kusá, H., Piccoli, I., Poesen, J., Stoate, C., Tits, M., Toth, Z., Wyseure, G., 2022. Impact of agricultural management on soil aggregates and associated organic carbon fractions: analysis of long-term experiments in Europe. *SOIL* 8, 621–644. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-8-621-2022>.
- Pavelka, M., Acosta, M., Kiese, R., Altirir, N., Brümmer, C., Crill, P., Darenova, E., Fuß, R., Gielen, B., Graf, A., Klemetsson, L., Lohila, A., Longdoz, B., Lindroth, A., Nilsson, M., Jiménez, S.M., Merbold, L., Montagnani, L., Peichl, M., Pihlatie, M., Pumpanen, J., Ortiz, P.S., Silvennoinen, H., Skiba, U., Vestin, P., Westlin, P., Janous, D., Kutsch, W., 2018. Standardisation of chamber technique for CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ fluxes measurements from terrestrial ecosystems. *Int. Agrophysics* 32, 569–587. <https://doi.org/10.1515/intag-2017-0045>.
- Pearsons, K.A., Chase, C., Omondi, E.C., Zinati, G., Smith, A., Rui, Y., 2023. Reducing tillage does not affect the long-term profitability of organic or conventional field crop systems. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 6, 1004256. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.1004256>.
- Pelster, D.E., Chantigny, M.H., Royer, I., Angers, D.A., Vanasse, A., 2021. Reduced tillage increased growing season N₂O emissions from a fine but not a coarse textured soil under the cool, humid climate of eastern Canada. *Soil Tillage Res.* 206, 104833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2020.104833>.
- Pires, L.F., Borges, J.A.R., Rosa, J.A., Cooper, M., Heck, R.J., Passoni, S., Roque, W.L., 2017. Soil structure changes induced by tillage systems. *Soil Tillage Res.* 165, 66–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2016.07.010>.
- Poeplau, C., Jacobs, A., Don, A., Vos, C., Schneider, F., Wittnebel, M., Tiemeyer, B., Heidkamp, A., Prietz, R., Flessa, H., 2020. Stocks of organic carbon in German agricultural soils—Key results of the first comprehensive inventory. *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 183, 665–681. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.202000113>.
- Powlson, D.S., Whitmore, A.P., Goulding, K.W.T., 2011. Soil carbon sequestration to mitigate climate change: a critical re-examination to identify the true and the false. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 62, 42–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2010.01342.x>.
- Prairie, A.M., King, A.E., Cotrufo, M.F., 2023. Restoring particulate and mineral-associated organic carbon through regenerative agriculture. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 120, e2217481120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2217481120>.
- R Core Team, 2024. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. Available from: (<https://www.R-project.org/>).
- Reiter, K., Schmidtke, K., Rauber, R., 2002a. Estimation of symbiotic N₂ fixation by a low-level, large-scale 15N application technique. *Soil Biol.*
- Reiter, K., Schmidtke, K., Rauber, R., 2002b. The influence of long-term tillage systems on symbiotic N₂ fixation of pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and red clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.). *Plant Soil* 238, 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014240311597>.
- Rochette, P., Worth, D.E., Huffman, E.C., Brierley, J.A., McConkey, B.G., Yang, J., Hutchinson, J.J., Desjardins, R.L., Lemke, R., Gameda, S., 2008. Estimation of N₂O emissions from agricultural soils in Canada. II. 1990–2005 inventory. *Can. J. Soil Sci.* 88, 655–669. <https://doi.org/10.4141/CJSS07026>.
- Rummel, P.S., Pfeiffer, B., Pausch, J., Well, R., Schneider, D., Dittert, K., 2020. Maize root and shoot litter quality controls short-term CO₂ and N₂O emissions and bacterial community structure of arable soil. *Biogeosciences* 17, 1181–1198. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-17-1181-2020>.
- Rummel, P.S., Well, R., Pfeiffer, B., Dittert, K., Floßmann, S., Pausch, J., 2021. Nitrate uptake and carbon exudation – do plant roots stimulate or inhibit denitrification? *Plant Soil* 459, 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-020-04750-7>.
- Skadell, L.E., Schneider, F., Gocke, M.I., Guigue, J., Amelung, W., Bauke, S.L., Hobbey, E. U., Barkusky, D., Honermeier, B., Kögel-Knabner, I., Schmidhalter, U., Schweitzer, K., Seidel, S.J., Siebert, S., Sommer, M., Vaziritabar, Y., Don, A., 2023. Twenty percent of agricultural management effects on organic carbon stocks occur in subsoils – Results of ten long-term experiments. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 356, 108619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108619>.
- Soane, B.D., Ball, B.C., Arvidsson, J., Basch, G., Moreno, F., Roger-Estrade, J., 2012. No-till in northern, western and south-western Europe: A review of problems and opportunities for crop production and the environment. *Soil Tillage Res.* 118, 66–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2011.10.015>.
- Staley, T.E., Edwards, W.M., Owens, L.B., Scott, C.L., 1988. Soil Microbial Biomass and Organic Component Alterations in a No-Tillage Chronosequence. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 52, 998–1005. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1988.03615995005200040018x>.
- Stockfisch, N., Forstreuter, T., Ehlers, W., 1999. Ploughing effects on soil organic matter after twenty years of conservation tillage in Lower Saxony, Germany. *Soil Tillage Res.* 52, 91–101. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(99\)00063-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(99)00063-X).
- Stuchiner, E.R., Jernigan, W.A., Zhang, Z., Eddy, W.C., DeLucia, E.H., Yang, W.H., 2024. Particulate organic matter predicts spatial variation in denitrification potential at the field scale. *Geoderma* 448, 116943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.116943>.
- Surey, R., Lippold, E., Heilek, S., Sauheitl, L., Henjes, S., Horn, M.A., Mueller, C.W., Merbach, I., Kaiser, K., Böttcher, J., Mikutta, R., 2020. Differences in labile soil organic matter explain potential denitrification and denitrifying communities in a long-term fertilization experiment. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 153, 103630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2020.103630>.
- Tobiasová, E., Lemanowicz, J., Dębska, B., Kunkelová, M., Sakáč, J., 2023. The Effect of Reduced and Conventional Tillage Systems on Soil Aggregates and Organic Carbon Parameters of Different Soil Types. *Agriculture* 13, 818. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13040818>.
- Tuszynski, J., 2021. caTools: Tools: Moving window statistics, GIF, Base64, ROC AUC, etc. R package version 1.18.2. Available from: (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=caTools>).
- van Balen, D., Cuperus, F., Haagsma, W., De Haan, J., Van Den Berg, W., Sukkel, W., 2023. Crop yield response to long-term reduced tillage in a conventional and organic farming system on a sandy loam soil. *Soil Tillage Res.* 225, 105553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2022.105553>.

- Venables, W.N., Ripley, B.D., 2002. *Modern Applied Statistics with S*, fourth ed. Springer, New York. ISBN 0-387-95457-0.
- Venterea, R.T., Baker, J.M., Dolan, M.S., Spokas, K.A., 2006. Carbon and Nitrogen Storage are Greater under Biennial Tillage in a Minnesota Corn–Soybean Rotation. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 70, 1752–1762. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2006.0010>.
- Venterea, R.T., Burger, M., Spokas, K.A., 2005. Nitrogen Oxide and Methane Emissions under Varying Tillage and Fertilizer Management. *J. Environ. Qual.* 34, 1467–1477. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2005.0018>.
- Virto, I., Barré, P., Burlot, A., Chenu, C., 2012. Carbon input differences as the main factor explaining the variability in soil organic C storage in no-tilled compared to inversion tilled agrosystems. *Biogeochemistry* 108, 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-011-9600-4>.
- Volpi, I., Ragagnoli, G., Nassi O Di Nasso, N., Bonari, E., Bosco, S., 2020. Soil N₂O emissions in Mediterranean arable crops as affected by reduced tillage and N rate. *Nutr. Cycl. Agroecosystems* 116, 117–133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-019-10032-1>.
- Weil, R.R., Brady, N.C., 2017. *The nature and properties of soils*, 15th ed.). Pearson.
- Witzgall, K., Vidal, A., Schubert, D.I., Höschel, C., Schweizer, S.A., Buegger, F., Pouteau, V., Chenu, C., Mueller, C.W., 2021. Particulate organic matter as a functional soil component for persistent soil organic carbon. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 4115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24192-8>.
- Yao, Z., Guo, H., Wang, Y., Zhan, Y., Zhang, T., Wang, R., Zheng, X., Butterbach-Bahl, K., 2024. A global meta-analysis of yield-scaled N₂O emissions and its mitigation efforts for maize, wheat, and rice. *Glob. Change Biol.* 30, e17177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17177>.
- Yu, W., Huang, W., Weintraub-Leff, S.R., Hall, S.J., 2022. Where and why do particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) differ among diverse soils? *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 172, 108756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2022.108756>.